

22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardization of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport.”

Report A1.5.1

Review of the safety and venting requirements
for the different hydrogen sampling strategies (direct, parallel).

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Summary

This report is part of the activity A1.5.1 of MetHyTrucks. It gathers the main sampling techniques and the venting procedures that are being used in the field during a Hydrogen Refueling. It provides guidelines for performing a safe venting after the sampling.

This report was written by:

Name	Institution	E-Mail
Rémy MAURY	CESAME EXADEBIT	r.maury@cesame-exadebit.fr
Etienne BASSET	ENGIE Lab CRIGEN	etienne.basset@engie.com
Sven KAISER	ZBT	s.kaiser@zbt.de
Thor AARHAUG	SINTEF	taarhaug@sintef.no
Thomas BACQUART	NPL	thomas.bacquart@npl.co.uk

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1 Introduction

This report is part of the WP1 (*“Parameters influencing the representativeness of the sampling”*) of MetHyTrucks and reviews the current practices for hydrogen sampling in a Hydrogen Refueling Station (HRS). The aim of this work package is to investigate the impact of critical parameters (e.g. refueling protocols, flowrate, pressure) on the representativeness of the samples taken at a HD-HRS when using different sampling strategies (parallel sampling and direct sampling for the gaseous species, and direct sampling for the particulates). Hydrogen safety is critical at hydrogen refueling stations. The sampling exercise is not part of the normal procedure at HRS (light-duty or heavy-duty). As HD-HRS operate at a high flowrate and the downtime in their operation has to be minimized, safety is a key element of the standardization of sampling. The aim of this task is to investigate critical safety and venting requirements. Hydrogen sampling systems have their own venting strategies (e.g. portable vent). However, there is a need to harmonize or standardize this aspect of the sampling to ensure the safety of all the sampling operatives and to avoid any downtime at the HD-HRS. MetHyTrucks consortium has a large experience with sampling strategy and some devices are already used for this purpose. This report will review the best practices which are in place, or implemented, in order to propose a good practice guide or recommendations.

2 Description of the sampling strategy and venting on the existing devices developed by the consortium.

2.1 ENGIE

2.1.1 Sampling strategy description

To sample at the HRS nozzle, ENGIE has developed a device adaptable for stations delivering hydrogen fuel both at 350 and 700 bar. The ENGIE sampling device is PED (*Pressure Equipment Directive*) certified and equipped with a tank and includes two options for measurements during a refueling event: online measurements and spot sampling. The device has three inlets, one for sampling at 350 bar stations, one for sampling at 700 bar stations and an auxiliary inlet for preparation and cleaning. The device consists of three lines (see Figure 1).

Line A has a 55-liter type 4 tank to simulate the presence of a FCEV vehicle (*without communication protocol*) enabling to perform sampling following the common refueling protocol of the station without the presence of a car, line B is dedicated to the online analysis of oxygen and water after pressure reduction (from 700 to 1 bar) and line C is dedicated for the filling of the cylinder(s) after pressure reduction (from 700 to 90 bar). The sampling cylinder is a 1-liter two ended valves coated stainless steel cylinder. Two cylinders placed in series are commonly used.

The tank is transported with nitrogen at a residual pressure of 500 mbar. Before sampling at the HRS nozzle, the sampling device is flushed with pure nitrogen. The tank is filled with pure nitrogen at a pressure around 15 barG for stabilization. The pressure is maintained during at least 45 minutes before refueling (based on tank manufacturer recommendations). Then, pure hydrogen is used to flush the lines B and C of the sampling device.

Figure 1. Illustration of the different functions of the ENGIE sampling device

2.1.2 Venting system description

All the lines are connected to a mobile vent system (Figure 1). This system is a 3,5-meter-high vent mast composed of a 1-inch stainless steel tubing. The outlet is located on the top of the vent mast.

Figure 2. Mobile vent mast of the ENGIE sampling device

A purge valve is localized at the bottom to drain water (if present during rainy weather) before purging.

2 stainless steel flexible hoses allow to connect the sampling device to the vent:

- One dedicated to the pressure relief valve (collected in line B)
- One for the main outlet downstream the tank that reject gases during preparation, purge and inerting phases as well as the pressure relief valve (collected in line C)

Gases are rejected to the vent during 3 phases:

1. During preparation phase:
 - a. Nitrogen is rejected during around 30 minutes to the vent for inerting at a flow around 50 standard liter per minute (SLPM).
 - b. Hydrogen is rejected during around 30 minutes to the vent for cleaning before sampling at a flow around 50 SLPM.
2. After refueling and sampling with the hydrogen coming from the station, the tank is purged from a maximal pressure of 700 bar to a residual pressure around 1 bar during approximately one hour. The maximal gas flow is estimated around 120 standard liter per second
3. Then the device (including the tank) is flushed with nitrogen to remove the hydrogen before transportation. The lines B and C are flushed with nitrogen for 2 minutes each. Concerning the tank, it is pressurized with nitrogen till 50 barG and depressurized down to 20 barG. This is performed 2 times. The second depressurization is performed down to 1 barG before transportation. During depressurization, a mixture containing mainly nitrogen and also hydrogen is rejected to the vent during two periods of 30 minutes and 60 minutes.

2.1.3 Others safety aspects

A calibrated orifice is present at the outlet of the tank to limit the maximal gas flow rejected to vent during venting.

Two pressure relief valves (PRV) are present respectively in line B and line C. The PRV in line B enables to protect the analyzer from a pressure over 1,5 barG. The PRV in line C allows to protect the gas canisters from a pressure over 99 barG.

In order to design and select the hoses, calculations have been performed to determine:

- Maximal flow and maximal pressure coming out from the pressure relief valves to design the flexible hoses,
- Maximal flow and maximal pressure coming out from the sampling device (downstream the calibrated orifice) during purging phase (after refueling).

2.2 NPL:

2.2.1 Parallel sampling system

2.2.1.1 Sampling strategy description

The H2 Qualitizer (Linde, AT) is parallel sampling system. The system is planned without requirement for purging. The system is not filled with inert gas before use.

The sampling is realized in parallel of a refueling event. The sampled gas from the HRS goes through a tee splitting the flow between the FCEV and the sampling device. The gas sample passing in the sampling device has then flow, and pressure restricted to 120 bar maximum (pressure regulator and flow restrictor (diameter 0.33 mm) to achieve filling safely a 10L gas cylinder during a passenger car refueling event of approximately 5 min.

2.2.1.2 Venting system description

The venting and purging of the sampling system is realized through the HRS infrastructure except after the non-return valves. The overall volume of this section non vented by the Qualitizer was expected to be approximately 20 ml with a maximum pressure of 160 bar as maximum pressure of the regulator. The volume is purged by a bleed valve (Hoke) with orifice 1 17/32 in full open. As the bleed nut is turned, pressure forces the ball off the seat. Pressure is vented through a hole drilled in the nut, angled back toward the body of the valve. The flow shall be directed away from user (wearing protective clothing, especially goggles). While the blow down at 1 17/32 in is expected within less than 1 seconds for the maximum pressure and volume, the operator restricts the orifice opening and realize the blow down within approximately 5 seconds. Therefore, the opening during the release never reaches the fully open position. Using elab software, a blowdown of volume of 0.1L at 160 bar would be realized in 3 seconds if the orifice diameter is approximately 0.5 mm. This is a conservative estimate as the reservoir volume is 5 times smaller. The safe distance for an unignited release of this diameter would be approximately 2.4 meters horizontally to reach 4% hydrogen by volume.

Regarding the pressure release valve, the positioning is unclear in relation to the flow orifice of 0.33 mm. In case the PRV is behind the flow orifice, the venting will be realized in the condition of 160 bar

(opening of PRV) and orifice of 0.33 mm, calculation in elab software using similarity law identified a safety distance to reach 4% volume of H₂ equals to 1.6 meters horizontally (ambient temperature 15°C, ambient pressure 1 atm). In the case of PRV situated upstream the flow orifice, the pipe diameter/relief diameter orifice is limited by the flexible hose with internal diameter 0.35 mm. Therefore, the safety distance to reach 4% volume of H₂ equals 1.7 meters horizontally from the release point.

2.2.2 HDV direct sampling

2.2.2.1 Sampling strategy description

The system is inspired from ASTM D7606 with direct sampling from HRS set in maintenance mode. The gas is going through a pressure regulator set at maximum outlet pressure of 147 bar. For safety reason a safety relief valve is set at 175 bar. The system is made of 3/8-inch pipe. Therefore, the direct release from the safety relief valve going through similar pipes diameter would lead to a concentration decay up to 46.5m using similarity law. The released gas from PRV is going through a 4 meters flexible hose and then into a mobile vent of 3-4 meters height teed at the top and directed downward. The Figure 4 shows the P&ID of the sampling system.

Figure 3. HDV direct sampling panel without the vent stack.

2.2.2.2 Venting system description

The system can be used with two types of cylinder valve:

- single ended valve cylinder, the line purging through the vent is realised through valves opening without any measurement of the flow (controlled through valve but not measured). The volume of the pipes from the first two-way valve (just after the high-pressure regulator) down to the cylinder stem is estimated to 1L water volume. It is vented within 10 – 60 seconds depending on the pressure (20 – 100 bar). The cylinder is not purged as it is maintained evacuated. The vent valve situated close to the vent open between 0.5 – 1 mm to achieve this blowdown time. Considering a worst-case scenario for the release (orifice diameter of 1 mm and pressure of 100 bar), the safety distance to 4% H₂ by volume equals approximately 4 meters.

- double ended valve cylinder, the purge of the system up to the bottle is realised as for the singled ended cylinder (described above). A second step is realised to flush the cylinders (filling with system pressure and then venting through vent) using the double ended valve. A minimum of seven cycles is realised (filling/venting), the release gas from the cylinder is controlled via a needle valve. The venting from a 10L cylinder filled to 100 bar is realised in few minutes (considering 5 min as minimum). It is equivalent to an orifice 0.5 mm to blowdown the cylinder is less than 300 seconds. Considering the orifice diameter, the axial distance from nozzle to 4% H_2 by volume equals 1.9 meters.

Figure 4: P&ID of the sampling system.

2.2.3 HDV parallel sampling.

2.2.3.1 Sampling strategy description

The system is inspired by parallel sampling approach as described in Section 2.2.1. However, some modifications were implemented with a mobile vent in order to depressurize and purge the system accordingly. A metering valve is implemented instead of an orifice to allow different filling rate and vehicle to be used in parallel. The current system is capable of 70MPa light duty vehicle and allow the use of different vehicle and level of fuelling through the metering valve adjustment to the sampling cylinders. The sampling cylinder are 10L volume with DIN 477 N.1 valve outlet (single ended). The pressure regulation can deliver from 10 to 160 bar (set point) with a pressure relief valve set at 200 bar to protect the cylinders from overpressure. The upstream section from receptacle to FCEV nozzle is capable of 300 g/s at 70MPa and 120 g/s at 35MPa. Due to needle valve and pipe size, the flow to the needle valve reduce to 0.67 g/s (70 MPa) or 0.20 g/s (35 MPa). The objective is to sample hydrogen fuel during the entire refuelling of the vehicle. The schematics is presented below.

Figure 5 : HDV parallel sampling system

2.2.3.2 Venting system description

The system purge is realised through pressurising the system up to the valve controlling the release to the vent. The system is vented by the HRS down to the non-return valve before the sampling system pressure regulator (see Figure 6). The volume downstream this point is estimated to a maximum of 1L considering the flexible hose volume. The venting is realised through opening a needle valve without any flow measurement or monitoring. The venting is realised within 60 seconds using the needle valve to restrict the flow. The cylinder can be filled during a purge cycle to condition it, in this case the cylinder will be filled to low pressure of 20 bar maximum and then vented through the vent. The venting is realised in 10 min.

Figure 6 : Sampling system with the venting line.

2.3 ZBT:

2.3.1 Sampling strategy description

The Hy-SaM sampling device is a “gas parallel” system. Sampling is performed without overriding the refuelling protocol. Venting to atmosphere without a FCEV is also possible.

Currently, a new Hy-SaM system was developed for HD-HRS with the following limitations:

- Sample volume: Sample cylinders of either 2.25 or 10L is preferred. However, in principle all sample volumes are possible. Up to three cylinders can be connected for consecutive or simultaneous sampling.
- Pressure:
 - Heavy duty pressure line: 350 bar
 - Light duty pressure line: 700 bar
 - Discrete line for sample of storage banks: up to 900 bar
 - Sample pressure: up to 90 bar
- Mass flow:
 - Light duty flow: 60 g/s
 - Heavy duty flow: 120 g/s

To adapt the LD sampling system to HD, a 350 bar receptacle and nozzle will be installed and the piping sizes will be increased.

Figure 7: Schematic depiction of the HySaM parallel sampling system

2.3.2 Procedure of the sampling

The procedure and the documentation follow the Shell PtW system. For the sampling, different procedures for different use cases were developed in cooperation with TesTneT Engineering GmbH. In the following it is described briefly:

- ➔ Organization of the sampling at the station (**permission of the operator, erecting security zone** etc.)
- ➔ Installation of the system and connection to all belonging parts (vent, sample cylinder, FCEV, dispenser, **grounding** etc.)
- ➔ Purging of the system with hydrogen from the dispenser & **leakage test** while the system is pressurized
- ➔ Purging of the system with hydrogen from the sample cylinder
- ➔ Filling the cylinder to final pressure of 80 bar with hydrogen from the dispenser
- ➔ Releasing the pressure inside the system with the mobile vent
- ➔ Dismounting of the system and all belonging parts

2.3.3 Procedure of venting

For the pressure release in the sampling system, a mobile vent of 3m height is used which is placed with a sufficient distance (more than 5m away from anything) to the fuel dispenser and which is connected with a flexible stainless-steel hose (DN18 x 10 m). There is a procedure for venting which belongs to the general sampling procedure.

The vent is used for the purging step in the beginning of the sample process. For this purging step, the hydrogen from the station is used to fill the line from the dispenser to the closed needle valve at the entry of the HySaM to a pressure of 80 bar. After this, the refuelling process is stopped manually. The hydrogen in the line is used to pressurize the sampling system while keeping the cylinders closed. In order to do this, a pressure switch flushing of the system is performed by operating the needle valve at the entry of the system and the needle valve for the venting alternately for a defined amount.

When the pressure in the line is relieved, the system also will be purged with the hydrogen from the cylinders. Before the sampling, the cylinders are filled with hydrogen 9.0 with a pressure of 8-10 bar. After closing the valve at the entry of the HySaM, the pressure switch flushing with the hydrogen from the cylinders can be performed in the same manner.

The vent is also needed to release the pressure in the system after filling the cylinder when the final pressure of 80 bar is reached. When the sampling is done, the valve at the entry of the HySaM needs to be closed. After this the remaining pressure can be released by opening the release valve.

Usually, it takes about 30 second to defuel the system. The system itself has a small volume since it is a short pipe routing with diameters of 3/8" and 9/16".

It also is possible to vent the system with the central venting mechanism of the refuelling station. But until now, ZBT could not build up experience for this procedure.

Figure 8: Picture of the modified HySaM

2.3.4 Further safety aspects:

Inside the HySaM system a pressure reducer is installed which has a set pressure of 90 bar. This pressure is enough for the sample. To secure that the cylinders are not applied with a higher pressure than the design pressure, there also is a pressure relief valve (set pressure 100 bar) which would open if the pressure reducer had a malfunction. The vent line is connected to the outlet of the pressure relief valve. Inside the system an orifice is installed which limits the maximum gas flow. In case of an overpressure this limits the gas flow which has to be vented by the pressure relief valve. The internal diameter of the orifice has been determined at 0.3mm.

The new HySaM system has the possibility to take samples at a 350 bar heavy duty dispenser. To secure that the gas flow has the correct direction there is hand valve setup which excludes that the two valves at the entry are open at the same time.

2.4 SINTEF:

2.4.1 Sampling strategy description

The Qualitizer is a parallel sampling approach similar to Hy-SAM. The sampling system is the same than NPL (see Figure 5).

After sampling, the Qualitizer needs to be depressurized. This is done with a purge valve that vents the internal volume of the sampling adapter to air.

2.4.2 Procedure of venting:

The Qualitizer uses the FCV as sink and does therefore not make use of a venting stack. The depressurization step to air is only a small volume (mL). Technically, the venting could have been avoided for 700 bar sampling with a feedback loop allowing depressurization through the HRS nozzle.

3 General guidelines for a safe venting after a sampling operation at HRS

3.1 ATEX zoning

ATEX zones are defined by the European Directive 1999/92/EC and are used to classify work areas based on their level of explosion risk. The delimitation of an ATEX zone is based on a risk assessment that determines the likelihood of an explosive atmosphere forming in a given area. This assessment takes into account various factors such as the frequency and duration of the presence of explosive substances, ventilation, and potential sources of ignition. Once the risk zones have been identified, they must be clearly delimited. Delimitation methods may vary depending on circumstances, but here are some common options:

- **Ground Marking:** Zones can be delineated by ground markings in different colors for each zone, enhancing boundary identification.
- **Signs:** Signs and labels can be used to indicate the presence of ATEX zones and provide information about specific risks.
- **Physical Barriers:** Physical barriers can be used to separate risk zones from areas where explosion risks are lower.
- **Use of Specific Equipment:** Equipment such as lights, fans, and motors can be designed for specific use in ATEX zones. It's essential to note that the delimitation of ATEX zones must be regularly reassessed and updated based on changes in working conditions.

An area is considered ATEX as soon as it is used to store or handle flammable materials. The degree of danger of an ATEX area is evaluated based on the quantity and nature of these materials. The higher the level, the greater the risks, and the stricter the regulations.

The ATEX regulations are defined by two European directives:

- Directive 2014/34/UE (ATEX 95), concerning equipment used in ATEX areas.
- and Directive 1999/92/CE (ATEX 137), concerning the safety of workers in an ATEX area.

These directives require employers to control the risks of explosion on their site, just like other occupational risks. The goal is to ensure the safety and improve the health of individuals exposed to ATEX risks.

There are three types of zones defined by the IEC (1986), by the Ministry of Labor (1988) and by the Ministry of Industry (1991).

This classification is refined in the ATEX directive, which no longer speaks of zones but of categories of devices, depending on the probability of the formation of an explosive mixture, and two different applications depending on the nature of the mixture (gas or dust).

- **PERMANENT RISK:** The explosive mixture is present at all times,
- **FREQUENT RISK:** An explosive mixture of gases or vapors is likely to form during normal operation of the installation,
- **OCCASIONAL RISK:** An explosive mixture can only appear in the event of abnormal operation of the installation.

The ATEX zone can be summarized into the Table 1 below:

	ZONE	MATERIAL CATEGORY
GAS	0: Permanent presence	➔ 1G
	1: Occasional Presence	➔ 2G or 1G
	2: Rare Presence	➔ 3G, 2G or 1G
DUST	0: Permanent presence	➔ 1G
	1: Occasional Presence	➔ 2G or 1G
	2: Rare Presence	➔ 3G, 2G or 1G

Table 1: Classification of the ATEX zoning

In our framework of Hydrogen Refueling Station online sampling, the ATEX zoning should be limited to the sampling system itself (due to the MP cone and thread fittings assembly or double ferrule system, piping, valves) and the venting stack. It is commonly accepted and demonstrated that the sampling unit is Class2 rated (rare presence) whereas the venting stack is Class1 (occasional presence).

The cone and thread fittings or double ferrule system assembly are known to be correctly designed for tightness. The ATEX area surrounding the sampling system should be limited to around 1meter (depending on the maximum internal pressure).

At the venting stack exhaust, the size of the ATEX area is bigger. We usually have seen spherical area about 1 meter for ZONE 1 and 2.5 meters for ZONE 2 (slightly off centred – see Figure 9).

Figure 9: (left) ATEX zoning around the exhaust of the Venting stack, (right) calculation.

3.2 Appropriate venting stack height

The definition of the ATEX zoning area provides requirements for the venting stack height. The Figure 9 defines a height where it should be appropriate to put the venting stack. From the field experiments, it is recommended to increase the height of the exhaust to avoid any potential hydrogen going toward

the ground due to the wind. From the consortium experience, it is recommended to set up the exhaust at least at 3 meters (4 meters as a reference value – see Figure 10).

Figure 10 : CESAME venting stack unit – height = 4 meters

3.3 Wind consideration

Depending on the exhaust shape and diameter, the hydrogen flow could be impacted by the wind. During long defueling (more than 30 minutes) and depending on the wind velocity, it could be experienced that the hydrogen may be pushed back to the ground. Operators equipped with H₂ detectors could measure H₂ concentration up to 250 PPM (from our field's experiments) being located more than 15 meters away from the venting stack. The exhaust diameter is an important parameter since it drives the acoustic radiation (see Lighthill) but also the jet velocity. An appropriate balance should be determined to avoid too much noise for the surrounding areas without being too much influenced by the wind velocity. The wind velocity should be of the same order of magnitude than the H₂ exhaust to avoid any unexpected hydrogen concentration towards the ground.

3.4 Exhaust shape

The Figure 11 below presents some of the exhaust shapes that have been tested by the consortium.

Figure 11: different exhaust shape for the venting stack.

The exhaust shape can play an important role in the noise radiation but also for the hydrogen jet development. It is most recommended to try to have a top directed H₂ jet to be less submitted to the wind condition and the potential migration of hydrogen towards the operators and the ground.

3.5 Safety and protection

From a general point of view, it is recommended to properly establish a zone with fencing, tape at the vicinity of the sampling system and the venting stack (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: delimitation of the venting stack

All the operators must wear ATEX equipment and should have 4 gas detectors.

4 Bibliography

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